

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMOS****FIRST NAME: GEORGE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In this paper, I shall identify some key concepts relevant to essay writing and explain how important they are to achieving a good essay product. In giving a brief overview of essay writing, I shall limit myself to those concepts that could pose some challenges to me as a result of my previous experiences in studies as I embark on this journey of improving my writing. As a response paper, I shall restrict my sources to the main course materials provided, that is, ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack for Period One. As I argue for the importance of a good essay, I shall consider writing style, plagiarism, referencing, proper language to be used, and being faithful to recommended or required guidelines, as essential. Though, these considerations are not exhaustive, they will form as what I consider the barest essential minimum as contained in the course material.

2) ESSAY WRITING AS BLOCK BUILDING

I consider essay writing as block building. It is like putting together pieces of blocks and building them into a manifest structure. The structure of an essay is necessarily made up of many parts. However, essay writing is not just a convergence of ideas, but it requires bringing together specific ingredients into a structure that has an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3).

Further, essay writing entails using a specific language and a determined style to do the building. It takes into cognizance the proper grammar, syntax, and the usage of quotation marks, and so on. Further, in writing an essay, the writer brings to play the

ideas and opinions of other writers. In so doing, the writer applies means and ways of sourcing these ideas; hence, the writer makes use of proper citations and referencing. This is important because, as a writer, it is inevitable that I understand others' opinions and ideas on a chosen topic to compare with my main argument. The idea is to evaluate whether these other opinions enhance and reinforce my argument, or they bring into perspective other aspects of the topic, or they entirely oppose my main argument. Thus, as a writer, I must have a proper knowledge of citation and referencing.

More so, like a building, an essay undergoes various stages. There is the stage of planning, sourcing for relevant information, data, facts, and evaluating or analyzing them, before the actual writing. Like building blocks, writing an essay will require knocking off some "blocks" or readjusting them to realign with the main argument of the essay. This is what could be referred to as editing, drafting, and redrafting (EUCLID 2019, 5). I shall now assess some of those basic elements that make up a good essay.

a) Referencing Style and Consistency

There are different referencing styles peculiar to specific fields of study. Such referencing styles include, the Turabian-Chicago style, the WHO, APA, Oxford, and Harvard. A writer must establish from the onset the writing style he or she wants to use before commencing writing. I understand I cannot superimpose the rule of style I prefer on a field of study with specific guidelines and rules as to which style is recommended or mandated. The writer's choice of writing style is influenced by the field of study or intended audience, and other factors such as, whether the paper is to be written by more than one author (EUCLID 2020, 24). Therefore, I must pay attention to the writing style required of me in any given writing.

However, paying attention to rules of style could be challenging especially for persons like me who has the privilege of studying various disciplines with their required style of writing. It appears this is a challenge I may face in the course of my study at Euclid University, but it is a challenge I am ready to face and surmount, knowing how important it is to adhere to the recommended style. Further, it is not enough to adopt a writing style, it also requires consistency.

Consistency in the use of a referencing style is paramount as I discovered while studying the course materials (*ibid.*). For example, if I decide to use the Chicago rule of style, I am expected to be consistent with that all through the essay; and not to use APA style at some point and at some other point revert to the Chicago style of rules. Or if the paper requires that I use in-text citation, I am not expected to combine with footnotes in the same essay. Consistency is required in all aspects of writing an essay, whether it is the template to be used, or referencing, the language, or even in the usage of numbers and abbreviations and so on (EUCLID 2019, 25). In all, I must be consistent with whatever style I have adopted.

Consistency makes for good reading especially for a spectrum of readers. Consistency in writing style plays an important role in cases where various authors are

required to contribute to a single document either for publication or for a client, and in cases where a style guide is required or provide (ibid.). Therefore, in applying a writing style, I must bear in mind the need to be consistent in writing my essay.

b) Transiting from the UK English to the US English

I am making a point of the distinction between the UK English and the US English because it is my lived experience. I struggled with the difference, sometime subtle, between the Languages because, before I proceeded to the United States for my graduate studies, my education was based on the Standard British English. Thus, it was challenging for me to start almost afresh to transit to the mandatory usage of the US English. One of such differences I noticed earlier on was the date format. While the UK format is day/month/year, the US format is month/day/year. It was challenging because hitherto, I was oblivious of the seriousness of the differences between the two languages especially in academic writing.

However, going through the chapter of the course material on the differences between the UK and the US English and their peculiarities (EUCLID 2019, 24-35), the need to pay attention to this reality is now obvious to me. Apart from the fact that the choice of the language is encompassed in the writing style, it requires consistency. That is, if I make the choice of using the US English as I am doing in this paper, I have to be consistent in its use, whether in grammar, syntax, spelling, punctuation usage, and so on (EUCLID 2019, 29).

Further, the usage of commas, periods and quotations marks is of interest. The difference in their usage in the US English and UK English are subtle and I often take them for granted. I am to pay detailed attention to them because of the easily unnoticeable differences in their usage. Since they are “extremely important” (EUCLID 2019, 35), I must be faithful to the consistency rule in writing my essay.

c) Plagiarism

Plagiarism, the act of stating someone else’s published works or ideas as one’s own without acknowledgement, is an act to avoid in academic writing. Plagiarism is tantamount to copyright and intellectual property infringement, and it is unacceptable. As a matter of fact, plagiarism is “*a serious academic offence*” (EUCLID 2019, 4). Writers and authors invest much intellectual energy to formulate and evolve ideas. Therefore, they need to be acknowledged and properly credited for their work. Whereas every author or writer contributes to the body of knowledge to be shared, they expect to be given credit for their work.

While it is true that a good academic paper or essay must contain relevant facts, ideas, and opinions of other authors or writers (EUCLID 2019, 2), it amounts to nothing if such opinions or ideas are not well acknowledged. Plagiarism can thwart or mar one’s desire to ascend in the academic world. Therefore, no matter how tempting it could be, I

must avoid it at all cost. And a sure way to avoid plagiarism is to master the art of proper citation and referencing.

d) Referencing

The course material exposes me to pay attention to proper citation and referencing to not only to overcome the temptation of plagiarism but to master it as an essential quality and necessity in academic writing. My expertise in writing will be marked on how well I correctly cite my sources. Proper citation not only indicate that I consulted other sources and opinion in my argument, but it also shows that I gave credit to those authors from which I sourced the evidence either in support of or against my argument.

It seems to me that it is vital for me to get a grip of the Turabian/Chicago Manual of Style, since it is the recommended style in my course of study. Therefore, it is essential that I understand all details of the contents of the CMS Crib Sheet such as referencing including citations, whether in-text or footnotes, use of quotations, bibliographies, and so on (EUCLID 2019, 44).

Further, as I noted earlier, research involves sourcing of information from authorities in the subject matter or topic under investigation. And to produce a good essay, it is vital that I have a mastery of referencing to point readers, among other things, to those sources for further reading or research.

e) EUCLID's Way of Writing

What I have been presented during my first week of study at Euclid University has opened for me a new way of writing. Whether it is in the use of templates provided, the method of learning, or the technics of interacting with the computer and internet, has been uniquely outstanding. For example, the Basic ACA-401 Tutorial video for this course gives me a detailed overview on how to interface with the universities' website, especially how to use the templates, and how and where to find applications needed for writing a good essay (2019). Thus, I anticipate an interesting endeavor ahead, while bracing myself for the possible challenges that comes with learning new things.

3) CONCLUSION

From the foregoing, I have made the point that essay writing is like block building requiring the convergence of various parts to form a whole. To produce a good essay, all these parts must be considered in detail and all rules governing them must be followed. In giving an overview of essay writing, I attempted to capture and explain some basic concepts of essay writing. For an essay to be considered good, I must take cognizant of the rules of style, language, proper citation and referencing, avoidance of plagiarism, and consistency in the writing style.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

EUCLID. 2015. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial Video*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.